

The use of reflective practice towards achieving effective English language teaching at primary schools

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to explore the use of reflective practice by English language teachers in providing effective English language teaching in primary school classrooms. This qualitative case study involving six in-service English language teachers who were selected based on purposive sampling. The data in this study were collected using teachers' reflection logs and a series of semi-structured interviews with the English language teachers. Thematic analysis was used to identify emerging themes based on the codes gathered from the interviews and teachers' reflections logs. The results showed that the English language teachers used reflective practice erstwhile in preparing and providing effective English language teaching for the students. They reviewed what has been accomplished and identify constructive guidelines to follow to succeed in the future teaching. They have also been doing variations of changes in teaching based on reflecting on the quality of instruction, levels of instruction, using incentive to motivate the students and managing time equally in teaching and learning process to help the children in learning English language. Since there is no clear guideline for teachers who use reflective practice in their classes, this study provided some insights on the preparations and the use of reflective practice as part of their teaching and learning process.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Teaching English as a second language (TESL) has become a very rich area of research [1] as Malaysian teachers face a lot of obstacles and issues to teach the second language to the students [2]. In view of that, the Ministry of Education [3, 4] encourages English language teachers to implement reflective practice in their teaching “as specified in Standard 4 of *Standard Kualiti Pendidikan Malaysia Gelombang 2* (SKPMg2) to ensure effective teaching and learning is feasible in a conducive and non-threatening environment” [4]. This paper describes the requirements of using reflective practice for effective improvement in teaching English language at primary level.

The implementation of reflective practice would also enable the teachers to change their instructions in place of teaching their students meaningfully [5, 6] and to nourish their teaching professional development [3, 4, 7]. Reflective practice also help the teachers to widen their pedagogical and content knowledge to make sure the learning to happen [8] and to increase students' participation in learning process [9-11]. Through reflective activities and process, the teachers make sense on every part of their teaching and learning journey [12-14]

by hunting the assumptions which support themselves to frame their judgments and actions taken during teaching, while planning and after teaching [12, 13] to search the new ways to best support their students' learning [15]. The reflective practice process also allowing the teachers to use their cognitive, skills, values and abilities to craft their instructions by looking at themselves from different angles as the teachers always bewildered by their personal limitations [14]. Therefore, through reflective practice, teachers could think critically, be more concern, aware and flexible with their surrounding and context [16].

At the classroom level, successful English language teaching depends on a focus on four factors. According to Slavin [17, 18] to achieve effective teaching, teachers need to reflect and focus on the four alterable elements which is known as "quality of instruction, appropriate levels of instructions, incentive, and time" [17, 18] to achieve effective teaching. These alterable elements work best with reflective practice to enable the teachers to achieve effective teaching [14, 19-22]. Therefore, teachers should use reflective practice to reflect-for-action, reflect-in-action and reflect-on-action [23-25] to make sure they are able to provide effective instructions [7, 26, 27] to motivate the students to learn English language [28] and to fulfil the students' needs, pedagogical needs, curriculum needs and teachers' needs [19-22].

Achieving effective teaching is not just good instruction [29] but the teachers need to reflect actively and think critically on the intended elements as suggested by Slavin [17, 18]. In addition, Slavin [17, 18] as well as Darling-Hammond [1] found that reflected on accurate elements upsurged teachers' teaching quality for students' achievement. Thus, they suggested teachers to use reflective practice to be more flexible and creative enough [3, 4] to plan the teaching, to manage the classroom and to deliver the lesson by taking into their consideration of students' prior skills, information, motivation and time needed to learn the lesson [11, 24, 30]. In addition, teachers need to bear in mind; the students' learning process was affected by teachers' teaching styles and students' individual's behaviour, cognitive needs, thoughts and feelings [16, 31, 32] to enable the students to be active learners [3, 4] to learn, explore, discover and create a better understanding of the subject they learn [1, 19, 33-35] based on their learning pace [26, 35]. Therefore, how English language teachers implement reflective practice in teaching and learning process is needed to be further explored and highlighted to improve students' performance in learning and English language and to upskill the teachers and parents in the intended community. Besides that, the implication of practicing reflective practice among English language teachers will be useful to guide other teachers who are facing similar situation to implement reflective practice and facilitate themselves to improve and produce substantially larger learning gains. This in turn, it helps to improve students' learning and to increase their teaching effectiveness [3, 4].

Teaching English language to non-native learners is challenging [21]. The non-native English language teachers need to play their roles to manage and direct their teaching process effectively to make sure they are not just delivering the telling process to the students in the classroom, but they are teaching them effectively [1, 21]. Besides that, a discussion of students' achievement always begins with teachers' reflective teaching activities which is associated to improve students' achievement in learning English language [1, 10].

In the current scenario, teaching English language as a second language is compulsory in Malaysia but English language teachers lack of reflective skills and they need guidelines to reflect critically to teach English language effectively [22, 28, 36]. At the same time, these non-native English language teachers also need to be competent in English language to teach lessons in Second Language setting [21]. It is because the teachers who wanted to teach English language effectively, need to reflect on their strengths and weaknesses to enable them to improve their knowledge of the language to be taught in-depth [19].

Apart from that, the teachers also need to find the best reflective teaching and learning approaches to teach English to their multilingual students who also have a multiple language background in the classroom as well as unique complexities teaching contexts [37]. Based on these reasons, the non-native English language teachers need to reflect, make modification and improvement in their teaching as to make sure they are able to play their roles meaningfully to comply with the current education needs [4, 33, 38]. It is also necessary for them to implement some reflective teaching strategies such as class discussions, sharing stories, roleplay, and brainstorming sessions to avoid shyness and unwillingness to use English in the classroom [24]. Hence, the teachers also need to build good interaction between teacher and students by providing effective classroom management [20] to motivate the non-native learners to learn and to lessen their difficulties to learn English language [7, 20, 34, 39]. Therefore, the teachers need to reflect and discover appropriate solutions to create effective learning atmosphere to increase students' motivation and their competence in English [25, 28, 37, 40]. For the above reasons, it is important that this study be carried out to explore the implementation of reflective practice among English language teachers at primary school in improving their pedagogical competence and the effectiveness of teaching English in the classroom to enhance students' enthusiasm in learning English language especially in Malaysian context.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This research used qualitative case study approach [38] for the data collection. The research was carried out in primary rural schools located in the northern state of Malaysia. Their views, ideas and feelings concerning the issue of reflective practice were recorded in a series of semi-structured interviews and reflection logs for a period of two weeks each.

2.1. Sampling

Purposive sampling [41] was employed in this research. In term of gender, three of the participants are males, while the remaining participants are females. Their teaching experiences ranged from 19 to 32 years teaching English language at primary schools as stated in Table 1. The six participants in this research were selected based on purposive criteria [41]. They have good reflective ability and they were also available and willing to contribute, communicate their experiences and professional opinions regarding the objective of this study [38]. The teachers also have the ability of acquiring information, storing it and processing it to generate new knowledge while encompassing numerous stages during reflection processes started from attention, memory and perception, to problem-solving and decision making [14].

2.2. Research instrumentation and trustworthiness of the study

The items in the study instrument were adapted from several previous studies. The teachers' reflection log was adapted from Ahmed [42] and the interview protocol was adapted from Larrivee [14] and Sewell [27]. The items were modified based on the discussion with an expert in reflective practice [38, 41] before it was used with the group of teachers the study. Triangulation was verified via methods of data collection [38, 43] which were the interview, reflection logs, and field note to establish trustworthiness in this study. All the transcribed interviews were brought back to the participants to be member checked [38, 43] and the content was verified to avoid misunderstanding and researcher bias. The profiles of the six participants are listed in Table 1. Pseudonyms were used to maintain the confidentiality and identity of the research participants [38, 43].

Table 1. Profiles of the participants

Participants	Age	Teaching experiences	Gender	Ethnicity	Schools	Reflective practice activities
Teacher Amri	42	21	Male	Malay	Primary	Reflection logs, students' feedback, reflective dialogues
Teacher Anuar	49	28	Male	Malay	Primary	Reflection logs, students' feedback, reflective dialogues
Teacher Nazmi	52	31	Male	Malay	Primary	Reflection logs, students' feedback, reflective dialogues
Teacher Ira	40	19	Female	Malay	Primary	Reflection logs, students' feedback, reflective dialogue
Teacher Vina	46	25	Female	Malay	Primary	Reflection logs, students' feedback, reflective dialogue
Teacher Zila	53	32	Female	Malay	Primary	Reflection logs, students' feedback, reflective dialogue

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of this study were analyzed using thematic analysis as advised by Braun and Clarke [44]. The use of thematic analysis allowed the researchers to have a lot of flexibility in interpreting the data. Thematic analysis also enabled the researchers to manage the large data sets more easily by sorting them into broad themes. It also helped the researchers to avoid the risk of missing nuances in the data. Therefore, the researchers were able to capture the key ideas from the interviews transcription to generate and categorizing the codes into suitable themes. The themes acquired from the interview transcripts analysis were presented to two experts in the area of curriculum and instruction for their professional and expert opinion to approve the validation of the terms used for the themes. Their agreement was later calculated for Cohen's Kappa inter-rater reliability value which resulted in $K=.875$ which means there is strong agreement between two raters in checking the themes derived. The themes were then reviewed again before the final themes were established.

3.1. The use reflective practice in teaching English language

A thorough and rigorous analysis was to analyse the data from the interviews and reflection logs based on Larrivee's rubric [14]. Five themes were derived from the analysis to show how the teachers use reflective practice in teaching. The themes were: 1) Continuous learning to improve practices and learning outcomes; 2) Analyze the relationship between teaching practices and student learning; 3) Acknowledge students' knowledge, community values, interests and curiosity in the learning process; 4) Seek new ways to connect teaching concepts to increase students' prior knowledge; and 5) Acknowledge the justice, sensitivity in social and political consequences of one's own teaching.

3.1.1. Theme 1: Continuous learning to improve practices and learning outcomes

The teachers highlighted that reflecting enable them to learn and improve their practices and students' learning outcomes. It is evident from the interview with Teacher Amri, Teacher Anuar, Teacher Vina and Teacher Zila.

"The non-native students as for example in my classroom who come from different background, lifestyles and cognitive abilities could learn more effectively if they could understand what I teach them. Therefore, I need to understand them and find out the ways on how I could make them learn it and how they could manage their own learning." (Teacher Amri, interview, 13/3).

"The students who come to school carrying multiple prior knowledge and backgrounds which need me to concern about if I want my teaching to be effective. I need to concern on their differences and needs to improve their learning outcomes." (Teacher Anuar, interview, 2/3).

"I need to understand my student first especially about how they are thinking and how I could connect my teaching with their prior knowledge, the time they have and the exposure they have. This is important for me to keep learning and to make sure that they could organize and use the knowledge I taught in the tasks given during classroom activities or beyond the classroom efficiently." (Teacher Vina, Interview, 24/3).

"My students are unique. They come from different background and learning qualities which need me to set my mind with useful alternatives to capture their attention to learn and absorb the information taught." (Teacher Zila, interview, 3/3).

3.1.2. Theme 2: Analyze the relationship between teaching practices and student learning

The teachers also emphasized that reflective practice helps them to analyse the connection between their teaching and students' learning. The evident were gathered from the interview with Teacher Amri, Teacher Nazmi and Teacher Zila.

"I always aware on my students' feedbacks and gestures in the classroom. If they show boring face or confusing it shows that I need to do something with my instructions." (Teacher Amri, interview, 6/4).

"As I'm teaching last class at my school, I need to use simple English with my pupils. Sometimes, I need to translate my instructions to them. If not, I'm just talking to my self alone while my pupils don't know what they are learning and what I'm teaching them." (Teacher Nazmi, interview, 12/4).

"I believe that code switching and code mixing help them to understand my instructions as well as enable them to learn better than just parroting the instructions given." (Teacher Zila, interview, 24/4).

3.1.3. Theme 3: Acknowledge students' knowledge, community values, interests and curiosity in the learning process

The teachers in this study also create ambitious tasks to acknowledge their students' knowledge, interests and curiosity in the learning process by reflecting and learning from their reflection on how they could use their previous teaching and learning experiences in the new lesson to switch with the learning context and concerning the community values. The teachers claimed that:

"My students like to be praised. They keep competing among them to count the stars and good I gave them in their exercise books. They felt being rewarded and appreciate themselves." (Teacher Ira, interview, 13/4).

"If my students finish their works earlier which I call it downtime, but the others won't I felt that there is no point for me to start the new topic or subtopic, therefore, I let my students to spend their time at the reading corner and silently read their favourite book or play the board games." (Teacher Nazmi, interview, 8/4).

"Yes, there are a few of them who are good and could finish their work earlier. But it was unfair to start new lesson. So, I prepared enrichment worksheets and games for them which they were eager to do it." (Teacher Vina, interview, 19/4).

3.1.4. Theme 4: Seek new ways to connect teaching concepts to increase students' prior knowledge

The teachers in this study seek new ways to connect their teaching concepts to increase students' prior knowledge. They provided equal chance to their students in the classroom. They allocated enough

amount of time for their students to learn and for them to teach. In this study, the teachers used allocated time to plan a suitable teaching and learning activities on the particular lesson and to deliver the activities effectively to increase their students' prior knowledge. They also provided time for their students to engage themselves in learning tasks by doing individual task, peer learning activities and collaborative works. The teachers reflected that the process of transferring and using the input gathered in the lesson enable the students to increase their achievement and self-confidence. Therefore, the teachers claimed that:

"I plan my lesson before I enter the classroom. I divide the activities for me and for the students to participate. But sometimes I need to make adjustment during the lesson to give chances to all students to participate actively in the activities and to enable them to understand the material taught in the classroom." (Teacher Nazmi, reflection log, 28/4).

"In my classroom I'm using teacher's talking time and students' talking time. Teacher's talking time enable me to provide direct and indirect influences while students' talking time enable them to do the tasks, to response, initiate and reflect positively or negatively to me." (Teacher Vina, reflection log, 16/4).

"Looking back on what I had accomplish is important. It guides me doing the correction of a major component during teaching process to fulfil the students' needs. The outcomes help me in identifying constructive guidelines to follow to succeed in the future teaching." (Teacher Anuar, reflection log, 4/4).

3.1.5. Theme 5: Acknowledge the justice, sensitivity in social and political consequences of one's own teaching

The teachers also use their reflectivity to think critically and put emphasis on the importance of human values in their pedagogy which included justice, sensitivity as well as love, non-violence, peace, right conduct, co-operation, team-spirit, fellow-feeling, tolerance, democratic and truth to balance their needs.

"Provided equal chances to everyone in my classroom could avoid them from having heart feeling and isolation." (Teacher Amri, reflection log, 18/4).

"The critical incidents which occurred in the classroom is one of the key points for me to take note and to quickly make changes in the current lesson as well as in the future lesson." (Teacher Nazmi, interview, 21/5).

"The unplanned and unanticipated event that occurs during my class or outside my class tense me and it cause me to intently remembered about it and avoid me to repeat it again in future. Therefore, I do make changes in my new lesson by planning another relevant and acceptable activities to fulfil all needs." (Teacher Ira, interview, 30/5).

"My students' behaviors during the lesson deemed me to have a particularly helpful or unhelpful feedback in the given situation. My sensitivity being sparked by them to wake me up to be more sensitive and justice to behave them and fairness to others who are really want to learn." (Teacher Zila, interview, 1/5).

As the summary, based on the thematic analysis, Figure 1 shows clearly the codes and the themes on how the teachers use reflective practice in teaching. The themes were emerged from the codes analysed in NVivo Version 11 to answer research question one.

Figure 1. The use of reflective practice in teaching

3.2. The elements reflected by the teachers to make changes in their instruction

The data analysis on the second research question revealed that the English language teachers reflected based on their students' feedbacks, students' achievement, self-reflection and their own observation. Five themes were derived from this study based on Model of Effective Instruction by Slavin [45, 46]. They are teaching performance, students' performance, motivation, time management, and classroom management.

3.2.1. Theme 1: Teaching performance

When the teachers were asked on what were the elements reflected by them to make changes in their instruction, they replied about their teaching performance as the main element. Related to that, the teachers believed that teachers are the responsible person to route the direction of the lesson to be good or to be bad. They expressed that they were really worried about their teaching quality. They claimed that:

"Quality of instructions is important for me. It is a way that evokes my students' interest, critical thinking, and learning in a meaningful way. It also makes my students to become curious and excited about what they are doing when I provoke them during the lesson." (Teacher Anuar, interview, 13/6).

"It's hard to imagine, but the quality of our teaching transmitted nonverbally. I realize that, the tone of voice, facial expression and posture will convey what I really mean to my students. But I sometimes unaware of my own nonverbal modes break other heart as I different people have different level of sensitivity and cognitive." (Teacher Nazmi, interview, 3/6).

"Observing my own teaching and collecting my students' feedbacks are good activities for me to explore and improve my own teaching?" (Teacher Zila, interview, 23/6).

"I'm not always right. Mistakes will happen consciously and unconsciously. Let the ego being here, I need to be open to accept and listen to my students' voices and learn from others. I believe that, learning is persistent." (Teacher Nazmi, reflection log, 13/5).

3.2.2. Theme 2: Students' performance

The second element was students' performance. The teachers were intrusive about their students' learning performance as to make sure they were definitely prepared themselves and their teaching to help the students meet their actual performance. The teachers also believe that they are the role models for their students. For that reason, they have a big influence on helping their students to shape, create, support and establish their strengths, goals and knowledge to improve their learning performance.

"The verbal and nonverbal feedbacks from the students enable me to rethink and to reframe my teaching methodologies and choosing another suitable material to increase my students' learning performance. Their participation in the classroom and their learning outcomes influence my judgements to make changes in my future lesson and teaching." (Teacher Zila, reflection log, 1/5).

"I believe that my teaching behaviors have a big influence on my students' achievement and participation in the classroom and in their learning performance. The lower students' achievement causes them not to achieve of lesson objectives force me hardly to make changes to increase their achievement. Meanwhile, a higher students' achievement force and challenge me to make changes to use another effective strategy to maintain and to increase the quality of their achievement." (Teacher Anuar, reflection log, 10/5).

"The students' participation and achievement in the classroom assessments affect my teaching performance. Their feedbacks force me to think further to find another solution to help and to support them to establish their strengths and improve their weaknesses." (Teacher Ira, reflection log, 23/5).

"Being humble to my students help me to nourish and build their trust which soon build their self-confidence and motivate them to learn meaningfully, widen their knowledge, increase performance and build positive thinking towards learning English language." (Teacher Vina, reflection log, 31/5).

3.2.3. Theme 3: Motivation

The teachers believe that incentive could motivate their students to learn and participate in the lesson. They plied the motivation strategies to tempt the students. They claimed that:

"I praise them and put the stickers in their books to appreciate their good works. These enable me to make sure that my students are motivated and attract them to involve themselves on the tasks given." (Teacher Nazmi, interview, 3/6).

"Giving encouragement feedback to them provided positive output in their work and increase their motivation to learn English. Recognition and appreciation also play an important role in motivating them to learn this target language." (Teacher Zila, reflection log, 18/6).

"If the students want to learn something, we as teacher need to support and motivate them to do it. I'm also allowing them to play games and award them the stars for their good work and good deed in the classroom." (Teacher Amri, interview, 16/6).

Besides that, the teachers also claimed that, they felt motivated to teach when they felt appreciated by their students, school administration, parents and community members. The teachers in this study believed that being a motivated teacher is one of the fundamental elements towards an effective teaching.

"Motivation to teach helps me to put an effort to create and spark good wishes for me to teach my students." (Teacher Anuar, reflection log, 1/6).

"The support from the headmaster and parents enable me to do the learning activities with my students better." (Teacher Vina, reflection log, 24/6).

"It was a challenge for me to teach them which sometimes hurting my heart. I need ideas and support from others to cope with the situation." (Teacher Ira, reflection log, 24/6).

3.2.4. Theme 4: Time management

Time management was another important element included in their reflectivity. The programmes in school made them often overloaded with hasty programmes that interrupt their teaching time. They complained that sometimes they had planned something, but something else took place and they faced time constraint in carrying out the teaching and learning activities. They need to postpone and reteach their lesson.

"The dragging time of other co-academic activities during school time disrupt my lesson and my students' attention especially to those who are smarter as they were always being chosen for most of the co-academic activities. I need to repeat and the other students in the classroom get bored as they had learned about it before. Sometimes, they are shortage of time to engage in the tasks given as they need to do the practice for the co-academic activities. Meanwhile, for the weak students they had less time to engage in the activities as I need to shorten the time in every stage but they have a better chance when I'm repeating the lesson. As for me repeating the same topic make me unable to finish the syllabus on time and my students have insufficient time to learn." (Teacher Nazmi, reflection log, 5/3).

"The time management is important for me. As I need to start the lesson on time. If not, I tend to drag the time and unable to complete the lesson on time. I really don't like my class after the recess and after the subject which need the students to move from place to place as it takes more than five minutes for them to be ready to learn in my class and my students have less time to learn the material being taught." (Teacher Vina, reflection log, 16/3).

"Maintaining the momentum during the lesson is one of the fruitful ways of preventing pupils' misbehavior during the lessons and to ensure the smooth flow of the lesson." (Teacher Anuar, reflection log, 2/3).

Besides that, the teachers also agreed they need to arrange and provide proper time for themselves to plan, to teach, to guide and to allow their students to involve themselves in the learning process in order to learn the material being taught effectively. They claimed that:

"I try hard to provide ample time to the students in my class to give them chances to complete the tasks given." (Teacher Amri, interview, 29/6).

"Students will be more motivated to learn about a topic when they are given ample time to grasp the gist of the information taught in the classroom and to use the skills or knowledge taught with guidance as they could not do it on their own but they can do with teacher's help and guidance." (Teacher Ira, reflection log, 30/6).

3.2.5. Theme 5: Classroom management

The teachers in this study also claimed that reflective practice enable them to manage their classroom well. They are able to sincerely assess the needs of each student as an individual.

"I always aware on my students' feedbacks and gestures in the classroom. If they show boring face or confusing expressions, it shows that I need to change my instructions on the spot." (Teacher Amri, interview, 6/4)

"As I'm teaching last class at my school, I need to use simple English with my pupils. Sometimes, I need to translate my instructions to them. If not, I'm just talking to my self alone while my pupils don't know what they are learning and what I'm teaching them." (Teacher Nazmi, interview, 12/4).

"I believe that code switching and code mixing help them to understand my instructions as well as enable them to learn better than just parroting the instructions given." (Teacher Zila, interview, 24/4).

The teachers also reflected continuously before, while and after teaching to make sure their students were ready to learn and to make sure they were also ready to teach.

"Positive classroom rules enable me to teach my students with appropriate levels of instruction and to encourage my students to participate in the lesson. I need to change the classroom setting to avoid them from playing and doing other things during the lesson." (Teacher Vina, reflection log, 23/6).

"I need to lower down my level of instruction to make it applicable to my students. I found that it will be difficult for them to understand my instructions if I continue using it." (Teacher Amri, reflection log, 14/6).

"I need to be more concern with their readiness. It is an important feature to be highlighted in order to achieve effective teaching." (Teacher Ira, reflection log, 9/6).

As the summary, based on the thematic analysis, Figure 2 shows clearly the codes and the themes for the elements reflected by the teachers in making changes in their instructions. The themes were emerged from the codes analyzed in NVivo Version 11 to answer research question two.

Figure 2. The elements reflected by the teachers in making instructions changes

3.3. Discussion

Based on the analysis of the data, there are two major aspects of this research that need discussion. The first aspect was about the use of reflective practice in teaching and the second aspect was about the elements that teachers reflected upon to make changes in their teaching.

In relation to the first aspect of the research, the results portrayed that the teachers applied reflective practice to adjust and make changes to plan the lesson, during teaching and after teaching to reframe their teaching for future lesson [9, 36, 45]. Similar to Sua, *et al.* [17] as well as Lee [36], the teachers in this study claimed that reflective activities support them to be more progressive and enable them to increase their teaching quality [2-5] but, the findings showed that, rather than practicing reflective practice on their own, the teachers need ample support from the school administration to improve their practices in schools [17].

The support and collaborative reflective activities [23] will motivate the teachers in implementing reflective activities in their teaching and learning process which could ease the teachers' stress in providing effective teaching [5, 43] to increase students' learning performance and to fulfil the pedagogical, content and context demands [5, 14] based on their own pace and significant to the context as suggested by Jejo and Haji [24]. It is because well motivated teachers play their role meaningfully to convey their enthusiasm to their students [4, 31, 45].

Moving on to the second part of the research, the participants focused on five elements to make changes in their teaching. The quality of instruction, appropriateness level of instructions, incentive and time as suggested by Slavin [17, 18] were highlighted as the needed elements to help them to achieve effective teaching, but the teachers claimed that teachers need to focus on their teaching performance and students' performance [10], teachers' motivation [31] and classroom management [19, 25, 29, 35] to guide them to be more reflective, creative and to think critically to find relevancy in planning and choosing the materials [33, 45] as well as effective approaches [30, 34] to deliver their instructions successfully [10, 46-48].

4. CONCLUSION

In term of practical contributions, teachers should use reflective practice to increase their teaching performance to ensure they can provide and deliver meaningful learning experience for their students with the intention of increasing their learning performance. Thus, English language teachers need to think critically, reflectively and reflexively to motivate themselves, to accomplish curriculum needs and teaching goals. Teachers should also have a reflective attitude to enhance their current teaching skills by determined their aims for themselves and enable them to control their behaviour and their students' behaviour to achieve specific, measurable, attainable, relevant, and timely teaching objectives. As regards, the use of reflective teaching and reflective learning could capture the students' interest and attention in learning this target language. Consecutively, based on the findings, the school administrators should take the discerning initiative to promote and organise professional learning activities to increase teachers' reflectivity and reflexivity. In addition, the school administration could use professional learning activities as a supportive medium for in-service teachers to reflect and share their best practices in a collaborative way to solve the teaching problems, to contribute relevant ideas and techniques to achieve effective English language teaching.

In the same way, the Ministry of Education should also provide a set of reflective practice guidelines and coaching expertise to assist the teachers with reference to implement continuous, consistent and systematic reflective activities to develop teachers' professionalism. The Ministry of Education should take advantage of the findings to fulfil the needs of English language teachers, specifically in using reflective practice to gain a better understanding of their own individual teaching, to improve their effectiveness in the classroom as well as to acknowledge students' knowledge, sensitivity, social and political consequences in teaching. Compatibly, in term of policy contribution, the elements proposed by Slavin need to be took up by the Ministry of Education as a guideline to revise the current education policy to achieve effective English language teaching and learning. As a final point, in term of theoretical contribution, this study add another elements to Slavin's Model of Effective Instruction in the context of Malaysia English language classroom which need to be highlighted as important and relevant elements to guide the teachers to deliver effective teaching. Teachers need to reflect and make adjustments based on teaching performance, students' performance, motivation, time management and classroom management rather than focusing only on four alterable elements which is known as "quality of instruction, appropriate levels of instructions, incentive, and time."

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